

THERMAL PERFORMANCE OF KRESLING ORIGAMI STRUCTURES AS DEPLOYABLE HEAT FINS

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Abstract. This paper investigates the thermal performance of Kresling origami structures as deployable heat fins for enhanced thermal management. Origami-inspired designs offer unique advantages in heat dissipation due to their shape-transforming capabilities, enabling adaptive heat transfer solutions. The study focuses on both numerical and experimental analysis of Kresling origami fins, with the objective of understanding their conductive and convective heat transfer characteristics. Experimental measurements are conducted in a controlled wind tunnel environment enclosing a heated body with deployable origami fins. Further, a transient three-dimensional numerical model is developed based on the conservation principles of mass, momentum, and energy to simulate the heat transfer behavior. The results demonstrate that the use of Kresling origami fins significantly improves cooling performance, reducing the temperature of the heated body by up to 35.1% and 14.1% compared to a finless systems and traditionally finned system, respectively. Overall, the study demonstrates that Kresling origami offers promising potential as a deployable and efficient thermal management solution, especially in systems requiring adaptability and compactness.

Keywords: Kresling Origami; Heat fins; Thermal characterization; Deployable fins.

1 INTRODUCTION

Thermal management devices are critical for controlling heat flow in various systems, ensuring that components operate within safe temperature limits [1]. They play a key role in electronics, aerospace, and energy systems by dissipating heat, preventing overheating, and improving efficiency [2]. These devices can include heat fins, cooling fans, and phase change materials to manage heat transfer [3].

Deployable heat fins have gained attention in thermal management systems due to the increasing need for adaptable cooling solutions in compact and dynamic environments [4]. Traditional fixed fins often face limitations in applications requiring variable heat dissipation, such as electronics, aerospace, and renewable energy systems. Deployable fins, which can adjust their geometry in response to changing thermal loads, offer a more efficient approach by dynamically optimizing heat transfer. These fins can expand or retract based on operational demands, enhancing or minimizing heat dissipation on demand [5, 6].

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In recent years, origami-inspired designs have emerged as promising candidates for advanced thermal management solutions acting as deployable fins [7]. Origami structures offer unique advantages, including high flexibility, scalability, and compactness, making them particularly suited for dynamic thermal control applications [8, 9]. Their ability to undergo complex geometric transformations allows for optimized and controlled heat dissipation, providing efficient pathways for thermal management.

Several studies have examined the thermal characteristics of various origami patterns, particularly Miura-Ori patterns (see Fig. 1(a)), for their ability to control heat transfer through conduction, convection, and radiation mechanisms. For instance, Rehmeier et al. [7] characterized an extendable multi-layer insulation employing an origami pattern for spacecraft applications. The origami folds decreased heat conductance by 42% while increasing radiative heat by 236%. Similarly, Mulford et al. [10] studied the ability of Miura-Ori patterns to control radiative heat in dynamic environments. Subsequently, Iverson et al. [11] further compared the apparent radiative absorptivity of the Miura-Ori, V-groove, and hinged V-groove surfaces and determined the dominant geometrical parameters. More recently, Ahmed et al. [12] incorporated natural convection analysis to radiative heat transfer with respect to the Miura-Ori and W-fold origami. The overall heat transfer coefficient were experimentally controlled by changing the compression length of the geometry. In specific, compressing the Miura-Ori and W-fold origami decreased the heat transfer coefficient by up to 25.3% and 45.9%, respectively.

Figure 1: a) Miura-Ori origami pattern mostly employed in origami-inspired thermal management systems, and b) Kresling origami pattern proposed in this study.

While these studies have largely focused on origami designs that expand or contract perpendicular to surfaces, our work aims to explore the potential of spatially efficient origami patterns that deform parallel to the surface. In this context, we investigate the thermal management capabilities of the Kresling origami pattern, shown in Fig. 1(b). Specifically, we aim to understand the heat transfer mechanisms of deployable fin structures made of conductive metals and shaped as a truss-based Kresling pattern.

To evaluate the thermal performance of Kresling origami, we developed an experimental setup and a computational model. Experimentally, the Kresling origami was subjected to controlled heating and forced convection in a wind tunnel, in order to assess its heat transfer capabilities. Additionally, we constructed a high-fidelity computational model to simulate the experimental conditions and gain deeper insights into the mechanisms governing heat dissipation in this complex structure.

The paper is structured as follows. In Section 2, we describe the experimental setup, detailing

Figure 2: Truss based Kresling origami used in this study. (a) Expanded configuration, and (b) contracted configuration.

the design of the origami, and the configuration used to evaluate the thermal performance of the structure. Section 3 presents the development of the computational model, including governing equations, boundary conditions, and numerical approach. Section 4 discusses model validation and heat transfer characteristics of Kresling origami. Finally, Section 5 offers conclusions and outlines potential directions for future work.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The Kresling origami fins structure are generally made of aluminum and brass due to their high thermal conductivity light weight. The structure consists of two (top and bottom) hexagonal aluminum plates (fins) connected through rigid bars (i.e. linkages), as shown in Fig. 2. The ends of each linkage rest on one ball socket joint, which is, in turn, attached to the aluminum plates. Spring joints are added at the center of the outer linkages to allow deployment of the structure upon applying a load (axial or torsional) at the end plates. The design parameters of the structure are carefully chosen such that it can maintain two stable configurations: a fully expanded and a fully contracted position, as shown in Fig. 2[13].

The Kresling structure is integrated to an experiment setup to investigate its thermal management capabilities as depicted in Fig. 3. The system consists of a heater with a constant heat flux, housed within an aluminum cylindrical enclosure. The origami structure is positioned such that the aluminum plates can slide along the surface of the enclosure as the Kresling structure is deployed into one of its stable configurations. The heater, centrally located to promote uniform thermal distribution, is controlled via a variable step-down transformer to regulate the heat flux. Temperature measurements are recorded using thermistors placed at key locations on the surface of the enclosure to capture relevant thermal variations. The experiments are conducted in an open-ended suction-type wind tunnel with a cross-sectional area of 0.5 m x 0.65 m and a test section length of 1 m. To ensure uniform airflow, a honeycomb structure is installed at the inlet. Air velocity measurements are obtained using a hot-wire anemometer. This configuration of controlled heating and forced convection enables a systematic

Figure 3: a) Experimental setup inside the wind tunnel and b) schematic illustration.

evaluation of the heat management of the origami structure under varying thermal conditions.

3 COMPUTATIONAL MODEL

A three dimensional mathematical model is developed to investigate the thermal performance of a Kresling origami structure. The governing equations and boundary conditions are set following the experimental setup discussed in the previous section. The computational domain consists of both solid and fluid media, as illustrated in Fig. 4. The entire computational domain is shown in Fig. 4(a). The solid domain includes the origami linkages, the support plates, the aluminum enclosure, and the heater as displayed in Fig. 4(b). The fluid domain comprises air which passes through these solid structures.

Figure 4: (a) Entire computational domain replicating the experimental setup, and (b) illustration of solid structure inside the computational domain.

3.1 Solid domain

Heat conduction in the solid domain is governed by the transient energy equation:

$$\rho_s c_{p,s} \frac{\partial T_s}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot (k_s \nabla T_s) + Q_s \quad (1)$$

where ρ_s , $c_{p,s}$, and k_s denote the density, specific heat capacity, and thermal conductivity of the solid, respectively. T_s is the temperature in the solid domain, and Q_s represents the heat source term.

3.2 Fluid domain

The air in the fluid domain is modeled using the conservation equations of mass, momentum, and energy, as follows.

$$\frac{\partial \rho_a}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_a \mathbf{v}_a) = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\rho_a \frac{\partial \mathbf{v}_a}{\partial t} + \rho_a (\mathbf{v}_a \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v}_a = -\nabla p_a + \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau} \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{v} is the velocity vector, p is the pressure, $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ is the stress tensor due to viscous forces, and subscript a denotes the material properties of air such that.

$$\rho_a c_{p,a} \left(\frac{\partial T_a}{\partial t} + \mathbf{v}_a \cdot \nabla T_a \right) = \nabla \cdot (k_a \nabla T_a) \quad (4)$$

where T_a is the air temperature.

Since the Reynolds number is greater than 10^4 , indicating a turbulent flow, we used the Transition SST (Shear Stress Transport) turbulence model [14].

3.3 Boundary conditions

The model incorporates several boundary conditions to accurately model the airflow and thermal interactions in the system. These boundary conditions are applied as follows:

At the inlet, an air velocity of 8 m/s is imposed along with a specified temperature of 25.5°C. The velocity and temperature boundary conditions are given by:

$$v_{\text{inlet}} = 8 \text{ m/s}, \quad T_{\text{inlet}} = 25.5^\circ\text{C}, \quad (5)$$

where v_{inlet} is the velocity magnitude normal to the inlet boundary, and T_{inlet} is the specified inlet temperature to the wind tunnel.

The boundary conditions at the outlet are given as:

$$p_{\text{outlet}} = 0, \quad \nabla T \cdot \mathbf{n}|_{\text{outlet}} = 0, \quad (6)$$

where p_{outlet} is the gauge pressure and \mathbf{n} is a normal vector to a boundary.

At the interface where the solid structures interact with the airflow, no-slip conditions are enforced. This is expressed as:

$$\mathbf{v}_a = 0. \quad (7)$$

Additionally, to ensure heat continuity, thermal coupling between the solid and the air is set as:

$$T_s = T_a, \quad k_s \frac{\partial T_s}{\partial n} = k_a \frac{\partial T_a}{\partial n} \quad (8)$$

At the far boundary, the fluid is assumed to move with the same velocity as the inlet velocity, and a zero temperature gradient normal to the boundary is imposed to prevent artificial heat accumulation or loss. These conditions are described by:

$$\mathbf{v}_{\text{far}} = \mathbf{v}_{\text{inlet}}, \quad \left. \frac{\partial T}{\partial n} \right|_{\text{far}} = 0 \quad (9)$$

where \mathbf{v}_{far} is the velocity vector at the far boundary and $\left. \frac{\partial T}{\partial n} \right|_{\text{far}}$ is the normal temperature gradient.

3.4 Numerical methods

The computational domain and mesh were generated using ANSYS Workbench 18.1. A detailed geometry was constructed to capture the complex structure of the origami-based system, which includes both solid and fluid domains. The mesh was refined in critical regions, particularly within the narrow air gaps between origami members, to ensure accurate resolution of temperature and velocity gradients.

Model computation of the governing equations, along with the boundary and initial conditions, was performed using ANSYS Fluent. The fluid domain, composed of more than 1×10^7 cells, allowed for a fine resolution of the buoyancy-driven air flow. A mesh independence study was conducted by varying the total number of cells.

The transient simulations were run for a sufficient number of time steps to capture the steady-state behavior of the system, ensuring the convergence of both thermal and fluid flow fields. The time step was gradually increased from 0.1 s to 6 s to maintain solution stability during the initial stages of the simulation, allowing the model to adapt to the transient behavior of the system. The residuals for convergence were set at 1×10^{-4} for all variables, except for the energy equation, where a stricter convergence criterion of 1×10^{-8} was applied to ensure accurate temperature

4 RESULTS

Before analyzing the thermal management performance, it is essential to validate that our computational model accurately reproduces the experimental results. Following this validation, we proceed to analyze the thermal response of the Kresling origami in both expanded and contracted configurations.

4.1 Model validation

The computational model was validated against the experiments for two cases; namely a bare enclosure and an origami in the fully expanded configurations. In both the experiments and the computation, the velocity is set to 8 m/s, and the initial room temperature is set to 313 K. A constant heat flux of 16 Watts is maintained at the center of the enclosure. The temperature field in experimental measurements and numerical model were allowed to develop until reaching a steady state. Fig. 5 shows the time history of the temperature difference between the enclosure and inlet temperature, ΔT , against the experimental observations. It can be clearly seen that the two cases demonstrate a strong

agreement between the computational results and the experimental data. Nevertheless, the results of the base case with no fin is less accurate, possibly due to the noise heat of the structural support in the experiment. Introducing origami structure may have increased the heat transfer rate from the enclosure container; consequently, the effect of noise heat becomes lower, and the mathematical results match within less than 5% of experimental measurements.

Figure 5: Model validation against experimental measurements with respect to the temperature difference between the container and inlet temperature, ΔT , for two cases: a) only heater without fins and b) adding support plates with expanded origami members.

4.2 Discussion and analysis

The validated computational model is now employed to understand the thermal characteristics of the Kresling origami as a deployable fin over a heated body. The cooling ability of origami fins is a critical design criteria to justify its application in thermal management systems. Accordingly, the temperature of the heated body is monitored with respect to the inlet temperature for four different cases: 1) mere enclosure, 2) top and bottom support plates without origami linkages, 3) enclosure covered by expanded Kresling origami configuration, and finally 4) enclosure covered by contracted Kresling origami configuration. Thermal performance of all cases are compared at transient and steady states in Fig. 6.

The transient period where the temperature regime is developing is shorter in the presence of fins due to their faster heat transfer rate. In specific, the steady-state temperature is reached within around 15 minutes in the finned scenarios as compared to around 25 minutes with no fins. Thus, introducing fins can speed up the thermal performance by up to 40%. Nonetheless, adding origami members in contracted or expanded states does not seem to affect the duration of the transient period. At steady state, the inclusion of fins significantly reduces the temperature of the heated body, with performance varying based on the fin configuration. Traditional fins without origami members lower the temperature by 24.6%. When the origami linkages are in the expanded configuration, the temperature decreases further by 29.3%. The best cooling performance occurs with the origami members in the contracted configuration, reducing the temperature by 35.1%. Compared to the traditionally finned system, the contracted configuration offers a 14.1% improvement over the expanded configuration. This enhanced cooling is due to the closer proximity of the origami members to the heated body in the contracted state, which increases convective heat transfer, as well as direct contact at the middle of the origami members thereby enhancing heat conduction.

Figure 6: Cooling performance of the heated body in various cases, where ΔT is the difference between the container surface temperature and air inlet temperature.

The contribution of combined conductive and convective heat transfer rate due to origami members can be further investigated. Since heat radiation is insignificant in this study, the total heat transfer rate away from the heated body can be expressed as

$$\dot{Q}_{total} = \dot{Q}_{conduction} + \dot{Q}_{convection} \quad (10)$$

The combined conductive and convective heat transfer from the support plates reduces the temperature of the heated body by 24.6%, as previously discussed. The additional cooling resulting from the origami linkages is primarily due to the enhanced convective heat transfer across these members. In the expanded configuration, convective heat transfer contributes to an additional 4.8% reduction in temperature. Notably, this percentage doubles to approximately 10.5% in the contracted configuration.

Overall, Kresling origami structures have shown excellent heat extraction capabilities. Compared to conventional fins, these origami configurations improve thermal performance by enhancing convective and conductive heat transfer mechanisms. Although this study focuses on the thermal behavior of Kresling origami, it is important to highlight their deployability. This characteristic makes them a promising solution for thermal management. For example, these Kresling structure can be operated passively or actively for thermal management of batteries, solar panels, and other electronic devices. Future work will focus on real-time analysis of thermal management applications.

5 CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates the significant potential of Kresling origami structures as deployable heat fins for advanced thermal management. Both experimental and numerical methods were conducted. The experiment comprises a wind-tunnel which houses origami members over a heated element. The numerical model was derived based on the conservation principles of mass, momentum, and energy, and then validated within 5% against experimental measurements. The model was then employed to analyze the thermal performance of these origami structures under varying configurations. The following findings are observed:

- Incorporating Kresling origami fins greatly enhances cooling efficiency, lowering the temperature

of the heated body by up to 35.1% compared to a finless system, and by 14.1% when compared to conventionally finned systems.

- Combined convective and conductive heat transfer rate attributed to contracted origami configuration is almost double that of expanded origami configurations.

In conclusion, the research demonstrates that Kresling origami structures can provide adaptable and efficient thermal management by leveraging their reconfigurable geometry. Future research could focus on refining the geometry for specific thermal applications, as well as investigating potential control mechanisms for real-time adjustments based on heat load conditions.

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